

BfR calculator for estimating consumer exposure to biocide residues in food

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Regulation (EU) No. 528/2012 requires that a risk assessment is performed for products containing biocidal active substances. The assessment includes the evaluation of residues in food and feed. Through the use of biocides in domestic households by non-professional users food can be exposed. This may occur either via direct exposure of food or upon contact of food items with biocide residues deposited on surfaces.

With active participation of the Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) the Working Group ARTFood (Biocidal Product Committee Adhoc Working Group for the **A**ssessment of **R**esidue **T**ransfer into **F**oods) of the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) has developed the “Draft Guidance on Estimating Dietary Risk from Transfer of Biocidal Active Substances into Foods – Non-professional Uses” (Draft Guidance Non-Prof Use). The draft document has been published on the ECHA website [1].

The Draft Guidance Non-Prof Use proposes models for estimating consumer exposure to biocidal active substances in their food. In order to facilitate the performance of these exposure estimates the BfR has developed an Excel-based tool for calculating the exposure for various scenarios. Calculations are based on assumptions and default values as described in the Draft Guidance Non-Prof Use. Calculator and the draft guidance are intended to support competent authorities and industry in the estimation of dietary risk to humans from biocidal products that are used in domestic environments (households) and could contaminate food.

1 Consumer Information on Biocidal Product Regulation (EU) No. 528/2012

Biocidal products are applied to control harmful organisms, while at the same time they could pose a potential risk to humans and the environment. Therefore the Biocidal Product Regulation (EU) No. 528/2012 stipulates that during biocidal product authorisation a risk assessment is performed. The Biocidal Product Regulation also applies to biocidal products used in private domestic settings [2,3], e.g. disinfectants or insecticides. For further information please visit the BfR-Webpage http://www.bfr.bund.de/en/biocidal_products_and_treated_goods-568.html

In case the use of a biocidal product may lead to residues in food, the risk assessment in the framework of the product authorization includes an evaluation of the consumer safety following the intake of residues in food.

2 Information on the ARTFood Guidance Document provided by ECHA

With active participation of the BfR, the Working Group ARTFood (Biocidal Product Committee Adhoc Working Group for the **A**ssessment of **R**esidue **T**ransfer into **F**oods) of the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) has developed the “Draft Guidance on Estimating Dietary Risk from Transfer of Biocidal Active Substances into Foods – Non-professional Uses” (Draft Guidance Non-Prof Use). The document is intended to support competent authorities and industry and describes harmonised approaches for estimating consumer exposure to biocide residues in food which may result from the use of biocide products in domestic environments (households).

The ARTFood draft Guidance Document has been made available by the ECHA on the internet in June 2015 [1] and is open for commenting for a one-year period. This will allow all con-

cerned parties (authorities of assessment, applicants and the competent public) to gain experience with the approach proposed and to send their comments and feedback if required.

For estimating the consumer exposure via the transfer of biocidal active substances used in domestic households (non-professional uses) into food, the Guidance Document proposes a stepwise approach. An important step within this procedure is the estimation of consumer exposure based on modelling.

The calculation of the intake of biocide residues by consumers is based on the contaminated surface area which could get in contact with food rather than on food consumption data since there is no data available on the migration of biocidal active substances from contaminated surface areas into food. The only exceptions are the scenarios involving exposure of drinking water. They include water consumption rates in the calculation. Accordingly to the requirements of the ARTFood draft Guidance Document consumer exposure is calculated for adults (60 kg bodyweight) and toddlers (10 kg body weight).

The calculation is based on essential information on the intended use of the biocidal product as well as on assumptions and default values as explained in the Draft Guidance Non-prof Use. If justified, e.g. if measured values are available for certain parameters, default values may be replaced accordingly.

3 Content and purpose of the BfR Calculator

In order to support and advance the use of the new Guidance Document, BfR has developed an Excel-based tool for calculating the consumer exposure. The BfR calculator for estimating consumer exposure to biocide residues in food as a consequence to the use of biocidal products in domestic households is intended to facilitate the exposure estimation in accordance with the ARTFood draft Guidance Document. The exposure scenarios currently considered are not a comprehensive collection and the list may be extended since adjustment of existing scenarios or development of new scenarios may be required on a case-by-case basis. For evaluation it should be ensured that the chosen scenario is applicable to the intended use to be evaluated. The BfR calculator also provides an overview of parameters applied in the models. Moreover, it contains example calculations that illustrate the calculations presented in the Draft Guidance on Estimating Dietary Risk from Transfer of Biocidal Active Substances into Foods – Non-professional Uses” (Draft Guidance Non-Prof Use). Examples include surface disinfection, spraying of insecticides, disinfection of drinking water and its containers as well as dishwashing. The calculator can be downloaded from the BfR website:

<http://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/349/bfr-calculator-for-estimating-consumer-exposure-to-biocide-residues-in-food.zip>

4 References

[1] ARTFood Draft Guidance on Estimating Dietary Risk from Transfer of Biocidal Active Substances into Foods - Non-professional Uses

http://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/15623299/artfood_draft_guidance_project_en.pdf

[2] C. Pieper et al. HygMed 2014; 39 (3): 68-76. Antimikrobielle Produkte im Haushalt – eine Betrachtung zu Auswirkungen auf Gesundheit und Umwelt sowie zum Nutzen für den Anwender, <http://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/343/antimikrobielle-produkte-im-haushalt.pdf>

[3] BfR (2003). Desinfektionsmittel nur mit Vorsicht einsetzen! 13.11.2013

http://www.bfr.bund.de/de/presseinformation/2003/24/desinfektionsmittel_nur_mit_vorsicht_einsetzen_-2336.html